

The narrative of experience: Modelling user experience through the use of literary narratives for the construction of the user journey

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Abstract

One of the greatest challenges of the service centred economy is the creation of meaningful and gratifying customer experiences. A result of all the interaction of a client with a company, an experience must be able to affect positively the feelings of the customer that is buying or consuming a service, consequently raising his acceptance towards it.

The methodology presented in this article offers a new way to analyze and model an experience, through a multidisciplinary approach based on design principles. Our proposition is supported by a tool applied for the analysis and planning of use cases, also known as user journeys, with the use of literary narrative references for the creation or improvement of consumer experiences during the delivery of a service. The method offers great flexibility in practical situations, allowing it to be applied in different contexts for the creation of the user's journey, provoking and exploring different feelings in a structured way across the whole experience.

Conference theme: Modelling Experience

Keywords: service design, user journey, myths, narrative, customer experience.

Introduction

The constant growth of the service sector during the last decades is transforming the markets worldwide through a shift from a product based economy to a service based one. “The fast pace of technological development and the increase of competitiveness makes the achievement of strategic competitive advantage more difficult if only through physical products. At the same time, customers are becoming more demanding. They not only expect to receive high quality goods; they also expect to receive high quality services with them” (ZEITHAML, 2001). The increasing competition in the service sector requires from the companies to improve their value offer and provide remarkable experiences to their customers in order to compete in the market and to keep their customer satisfied.

In services, design can work as an agent that promotes and facilitates interaction between the company and its customers. The role of design in this context is to translate the customers’ problems and their real needs and wants to the company, and to communicate the philosophy and value proposal of the company to its customers, either through products, services or other points of interaction. Since production and consumption occurs at the same time, the interaction between customers and companies becomes an active process, and therefore, the participation of the customers in it is essential.

Recently, service organizations have turned their attention to the fact that design thinking could be applied to services in order to create better experiences to their users. Service design, or design of services, can work as a tool to shape the customer experience and create interaction models for the companies, foreseeing the choices users might have during the process and which emotions and feelings might arouse from them. Thinking on a service through a design process allows the service company or who is planning a service to have a better understanding of the users and provides insights on ways to approach them in a more creative and efficacious way.

An objective of service design is to plan the user experience, utilizing several methodologies such as ethnographic research, user observation, use case analysis and interaction models for the definition of service and its delivery, combined in a process that also involves methodologies from other knowledge areas, like administration, communication, psychology and others. This combination of different techniques can be easily applied on the service sphere to bound problems, what is commonly called problem setting, and further help as information source to solve these very problems. The advantages of these methodologies are the approximation to the

user environment and the results are normally very effective, being possible to identify detailed information about the user's needs.

One tool that can be useful for designing services and experiences is the framework of a user journey. The user journey is a scheme that represents all the actions a user must perform to use a service. "That journey starts from, say, becoming aware of the proposition, and then moving on to engage with it, and then potentially moving on to join it. There's some value that the consumer gets from the proposition, like feeling smart, and eventually they may move on to advocacy. This can potentially become a virtuous circle" (SAMALIONIS in MOGGRIDGE, 2006). The user journey considers the context and the user's capabilities, all the steps and activities he executes to accomplish a specific result, identifying the experiences and touch points before and after the service delivery and defining the relationship between users' goals and the company's product or service offer. Besides, the journey also helps to identify the different channels used by the company to reach or serve its public, as well as problems and bottlenecks during the performance of this service.

The user participation in a service can be very intense and involve many personal and emotional aspects, generating a sort of individual story for each one of them. This premise allows us to think and shape services as stories that follow a plan and promote interaction between different actors and environments. In literature, the mythic narrative, basis of all modern narratives, is a genre that presents a high relevance of psychological and emotional aspects. A myth is a metaphor, a comparison that helps us to understand aspects of our own personality. These stories are models of how the human mind works, psychologically true and emotionally real (Vogler, 1992).

We consider that through the analogy of the user journey to literary narratives, in special mythic narratives, it is possible to create and plan a linear and structured experience, exploring different aspects of human behaviour in a continuous way, adding a greater significance to the service and therefore increasing its level of satisfaction. The use of narrative elements such as characters, challenges and rewards creates a more immersive experience, where the user acts as the leading character, and the service staff, infrastructure and physical evidences are interconnected in a single and structured scheme.

Building a user journey

The user journey is in a way similar to an ethnographic observation, and its building requires from the beginning to watch carefully the user's behaviour on his own environment: what are

his needs, expectations and impressions regarding the service and which feelings or attitudes stimulate him to start the journey. When considering an existing service, the user journey will initially reflect all the existing steps and activities the user and the company take in order to deliver the service properly. Through the journey building it is possible to identify all the actors involved, the choices and emotions of users, physical and digital elements, besides the channels and infrastructure required for the service to be delivered, and cross-relate it with all the information gathered from user research, in order to identify points of improvement in the current process and ways to approach each of them.

In case of non-existing services, the user journey must be created for the first time, taking into account the business model the company is planning to implement, considering logistics, channels and infrastructure selected to deliver the service, and all information gathered from user research. In such scenario, the user journey confronts the company's objectives with the users' needs.

In a user journey, it is important to understand the logic about these steps and why they follow a certain order. For instance, during the delivery of a service, sometimes the user participates in it carrying out activities and tasks that occur in a sequence. We might question if when the service provider structured this service, he thought about the order of the service steps on purpose. And what would change in the user experience if this order was different or some steps were eliminated for a specific reason or based on a reference model. The results of such changes can directly affect how users perceive the service, as Lovelock & Wirtz (2006) states "to speed up processes and eliminate unnecessary steps to avoid wasting time and effort are important measures a company can adopt to improve the value perception of its service".

The different steps ordered to form a service experience can be compared to a theatrical performance in which many actors interact in different ways to generate a story. "The analogy between the service performance and the elements of a theatre work gives marketing and management a model through which to design, manage, describe and classify services" (Grove et al., 1992). In dramaturgy, the human behaviour is interpreted to stimulate emotions and reactions in the public. This characteristic of creating sequences of facts or activities is based on narrative structures that originate stories, tales, myths, fables that have a direct connection to the human behaviour and psychological and cultural aspects of a society.

Observing the structure of the user journey, it is possible to identify analogue steps and similar elements with the mythic narrative model found in literature. These similarities are even more evident in services classified by Lovelock (2006) as people processing and mental stimulus

processing, in which actions, either concrete or intangible, are directed to people. The presence of a protagonist can be interpreted as the main user of a service in the journey. The idea that this character starts his journey in a way and during the process he executes some tasks, faces challenges and meets other characters (service staff or other users) in order to accomplish a certain result, being transformed by these happenings during and at the end of the process, is very similar both in the user journey and the mythic narrative, if not comparing them literally in all details.

The mythic narrative model identifies some usual steps of this type of narrative that represent in a linear form the course of one or more characters. The model has its origin from the studies of Joseph Campbell (1949), who analyzed the usual structural elements of stories, tales, movies and myths, in which different characters assume role or archetypes across the narrative. Based on Campbell's studies, Christopher Vogler (1992) on his book "The Writer's Journey" analyses the presence of mythic narrative aspects in several movie scripts and summarizes it in 12 steps:

- The hero is presented in his ORDINARY WORLD, where
- He receives the CALL TO ADVENTURE.
- At first, the HERO IS RELUCTANT, but
- THE HERO IS ENCOURAGED BY THE WISE OLD MAN OR WOMAN to
- PASS THE FIRST THRESHOLD and enters the special world, where
- THE HERO ENCOUNTERS TESTS AND HELPERS.
- THE HERO REACHES THE INNERMOST CAVE, passing the second threshold
- Where THE HERO ENDURES THE SUPREME ORDEAL.
- THE HERO SEIZES THE SWORD and gets to
- THE ROAD BACK to the ordinary world.

Figure 1: The mythic narrative.

The model shows the steps the hero needs to accomplish during his adventure, involving ceremonies and rituals during a process of self-knowledge in a continuous and linear way. It also presents characteristics and relevance of each step, participating characters and their roles in the journey. The hero's journey in mythic narratives starts when the protagonist is in an ordinary world. This main character must renounce the ordinary world to undertake an adventure or a journey for a reason, carrying out many activities in order to seize the sword, step when he must endure his supreme ordeal and face an enemy or an obstacle to reach his reward. By the end of the journey, the character returns to the ordinary world transformed.

The use of such analogy gives a new perspective to the methodology, either when reformulating a service or creating a new one, establishing a reference for the structuring of the service steps. Usually defined by a company because of practical reasons, both for the company itself and for customers, the steps in a regular journey are structured as a group of tasks that need to be accomplished for the user to receive its benefits. Thinking of a journey as a mythic narrative allows the service provider to structure the journey in a sequential way that involves actively the user, creating a higher meaning not only for the final result, but also for the whole process.

The mythic journey can help the creation of new services through the definition of a theme, a specific mood that permeates the service in each and every step. When relating the information identified by the ethnographic research with the user journey, service providers can better order the actions a user must perform, and in every step define the elements and characters able to tap the emotions of the user in order to create a greater meaning for the service experience. These characteristics can be translated through a service brief containing a general overview of how to organize the service, or through a service specification, bringing details of each step, processes to deliver the service, description of every service elements and characters as well as scripts for all points of interaction with the users.

When applied for the reconfiguration of an existing service, the mythic journey can work as a way to analyze existing steps, as well as characters and elements that are present in it, finding gaps and excesses between the existing journey and the mythical one. This analysis can then generate a new service blueprint, as well as a service brief and specification that address the main points or steps to be improved, translating the strategic positioning of the service into an operational plan.

Applying the method for modelling experiences in education

The methodology presented here was applied during a project developed for Unisinos Design School in Brazil. In this case, the narrative model was chosen as a reference to re-design the journey of the undergraduate students in a more continuous and linear way. The mythic narrative structure is also very similar to the learning process of students in higher education, involving ceremonies and rituals during a process of self-knowledge and personal transformation. It also helps to identify characteristics of each step, participating characters and their roles in the journey.

Observing the student's journey we could identify two distinct moments: one before purchasing the service, when people become informed and interested about the course, and another moment during the service delivery, representing the active participation of the students during the whole undergraduate course. This second phase occurs during an extended period of time, when different activities may be repeated many times. The student's journey was represented through a framework showing all the steps students need to cover and these steps were identified after interviews with the students and observing them in their everyday context at school.

Figure 2: The student's journey

The main steps of the current journey were tracked, starting from the user becoming aware of the need to enrol to an university. After researching about the courses of his interest, he chooses the design course. The student must overcome an entrance exam to complete the enrolment process and start participating on classes and other complementary activities. Then, the student must do tests and exams, deliver and present projects in order accomplish the objectives of the course program. He constantly receives evaluations and feedbacks about his performance and progress. Then, he experiences a professional practice through the curricular internship, arriving to his last challenge, the course's final project. Finally, the student concludes his journey with his graduation.

After mapping the current student's journey, we compared it to the mythic narrative structure to identify analogue steps and similar elements considering the narrative model as a reference. For a better visualization of this comparison another framework was designed overlapping both structures.

Figure 3: Comparison between the student's journey and the mythic narrative structure.

Through this framework it's possible to see more precisely the correspondence of the steps. Starting from the hero (student) in his ordinary world before undertaking the adventure (awareness). Then he receives a call and renounces the ordinary world to start his journey; in the student case, this is the quest for knowledge and certification (recognition by the society).

At this point, the hero is reluctant after receiving the call for adventure which can be interpreted as the student insecurity to start the course, or even during the course, his decision to give up. However this event may or may not happen, the hypothesis may have a strong influence to the student's experience in the course. Another relevant step, the encouragement by the wise old man may be interpreted in the student journey as a counselling with somebody, a teacher, the course coordinator, a professional of design, friends or family and can possibly affect the student's feelings and experience regarding the course.

These comparison and analysis process lead us to a wider vision of the current scenario and the problem boundaries. The references taken from the narrative can be very useful to build a new journey that is more continuous and linear.

In education, the mythic narrative structure presents a great similarity to the student's journey in terms of characters, activities, events and psychological aspects. However, the use of the journey diagram as an ethnographic observation of the service users has the advantage to be very flexible in terms of application, being a suitable tool for other types of services with a high relevance of people, for instance health care and transportation.

The process also provides a reference to the service delivery, giving a wider vision of it and more understanding of each step in this process. Each step presents remarkable characteristics and performs a fundamental role in transforming the user, considering psychological and behavioural factors of the involved actors. Besides, the new journey can focus more on emotional aspects of the experience instead of approaching it in rational and obvious way.

Conclusions

The model proposed provides a new and different way of designing a user journey for a service. The comparison with the mythic journey narrows its application to specific types of services, such as the ones classified by Lovelock as people processing and mind stimulus processing, best represented on the education and entertainment industries. It creates an important reference where there was none, exploring several aspects related to the users and the way they perceive a service. Even though some characteristics of the method can help the development of other kinds of services, the specific nature of the mythic narrative might not be suitable for services with lower levels of interaction.

While several companies and brands try to attract new clients by establishing their identity based on stories and experiences nowadays, the mythic journey matches perfectly this trend by widening the focus of services from an efficiency perspective to a complete experience that is emotionally relevant, positioning the user as an active part of this story.

The idea here presented offers new opportunities to interpret the user journey with the use of different referrals, be them from literature or other knowledge areas. It also gives a better understanding of the several actors and elements involved in each step of the journey, with the possibility to analyze them in a more complex way through other disciplines like sociology and psychology.

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